

Molecular Analysis of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* Metallo-Beta-Lactamase: A First Report of an Iranian Referral Pediatric Hospital

Shima Mahmoudi¹, Babak Pourakbari¹, [Mansoureh Hosseini](#)², Amir Esmail Alyari³, Mohammad Taghi Haghi Ashtiani⁴ and Setareh Mamishi^{1,3,*}

¹Pediatric Infectious Disease Research Center, Tehran University of Medical Science, Tehran, Iran; ²Department of Biology, Faculty of Science, Ferdowsi University, Mashhad, Iran; ³Department of Infectious Diseases, Pediatrics Center of Excellence, Children's Medical Center, Tehran University of Medical Sciences, Tehran, Iran and ⁴Department of Pathology, School of Medicine, Tehran University of Medical Sciences, Tehran, Iran.

Abstract

Introduction: *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is an important opportunistic pathogen which causes clinical infections among ill patients. Metallo-Beta-lactamases (MBLs) are important mechanisms of carbapenem (drug of choice) resistance among *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates. The aim of this study was to determine B-lactamases genes (bla-genes) in *P. aeruginosa* isolates and to detect percentage of MBLs among *P. aeruginosa* isolates in different wards.

Material and Methods: Clinical isolates of *P. aeruginosa* in patients hospitalized at Children's Medical Center were collected in two years using a sterile swab. For differentiation and identification of strains the BHI media, Sytrymaid agar and Oxidase test were used and Kirby Baure method antibiotic susceptibility and PCR assay were performed for detection of bla-genes.

Results: Based on the study results from a total of 269 isolates of *P. aeruginosa*, 39 isolates were found to be imipenem resistant. From these isolates, 19 strains of *P. aeruginosa* isolates were determined to be MBL producers by phenotypic method. All of the Imipenem resistant *P. aeruginosa* isolates were examined by PCR for the presence of the bla-genes. All MBL-producing isolates carried bla-IMP Genes. And the results of the antibiogram showed the greatest resistance to the Nitrofurantoin Nalidixic acid and Cotrimoxazole and Cefixime (100%) and resistance to other antibiotics was also significant.

Conclusion: Considering the prevalence and clinical importance of MBL producing isolates, rapid identification of them and use of the appropriate infection control measures are necessary to prevent further spread of them by these organisms and to help treatment of Infections.

Keywords: *P. aeruginosa*, metallo-B-lactamases, drug resistance, sytrymaid agar, oxidase test, nitrofurantoin.

Link: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/27915986>